

Analysis of Song "Tanganku Na Metmet" by Using Translation Techniques into English

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This study aims to analyze "Ende Tanganku Na Metmet", which is a traditional song in the Toba Batak language by using translation techniques into English. Translation techniques are the methods used by translators to convey messages from the source language to the translation language. Translation techniques can explain the essence of the object of translation which is applied at the level of words, phrases, clauses, or sentences. The theory used is the Newmark translation technique. This research method is descriptive analysis. The results of this study, the translation techniques used by the translators are 1) transposition, intrasystem shift (intra-category shift), 2) modulation, consisting of shifting the scope of meaning. 3) Omission. 4) Culture Understanding.

Keywords: Translation Technique, Tanganku Na Metmet, Ende, Song analysis

INTRODUCTION

The essence of work is very important to be able to understand work and art. The diversity of literacy can raise the curiosity of the essence of art for most people. To get the essence of art from literacy, the translator will translate literary works and produce translations. In translating text, translation does not only translate the text from the source language into the translation language. According to Nida and Taber (1982), the language translation is obtained in the first language into the basic language which is expected to also convey the author's message, so that the translator can translate and also produce the essence of translation. Translation skills are always related to meaning, elements, essence, ethics, and aesthetics. In more depth about translation, Nida and Taber argue that there are two things that are quite significant in the translation process, namely the essence of the message referred to by the source and the equivalence of essence without losing the meaning of the translation. Limited vocabulary, cultural incomprehension, and essence often make translations inaccurate. Mistakes in understanding translations that do not match the author's message will be very bad in the development of literary values. Nababan (2008) explains that the complexity of diversity is one of the factors that cause translation difficulties. In the translation process, translators often experience problems. In dealing with this, a good translation technique is needed which is effective in solving the problem.

The translation technique is a method used to convey messages from the original language to the destination/translation language, in which translation is grouped at the level of words, phrases, clauses, or sentences. According to Molina and Albir (2002), translation techniques have five characteristics, namely 1) influencing translation results, 2) classified by comparison with literacy sources, 3) at a limited level, 4) interrelated based on certain cultural contexts, 5) functional and has the intention and reason for the work to be translated. The use of good translation techniques will help the level of translation quality in determining the form and structure of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences resulting from the translation. In addition, the translation will also help determine the most suitable equivalent in the target language for translation. Thus, the equivalents found in essential translations can be applied in various languages. Then, the use of translation techniques will not only produce an accurate translation but also easy to digest in the mind or easily understood by readers of the language being translated.

Ideally, the variety of translations has different results from one translator to another. Translation techniques must have ethics and theories that must be put forward by the translators. Newmark (1988) is a translator who puts forward a theory on translation techniques. The theory includes transposition, modulation, descriptive translation, additional explanations, footnotes, phonological translators, standard used in translations, cultural equivalents, and omissions. To support this theory, Catford (1965) explains that in improving the quality of translation, transpositions can be seen in two forms, namely changes in translation levels and categories. Grammar and vocabulary levels often shift as the text is translated, while translation categories shift frequently. This is because the translation category contains word-class shifts, unit shifts, and intrasystem shifts.

In this research, the writer will use the theory of translation techniques in the song Tanganku Na Metmet which is translated into English. The song Tanganku Na Metmet is a folk song from Tapanuli-Batak Toba. It is done by the author to introduce tribal culture and language to the national language. The song Tanganku Na Metmet, is a song that is often sung by children in the Tapanuli area - North Sumatra and in other provinces whose families are Toba Batak language speakers. The author chose this work because Ende Tanganku Na Metmet is a song that is often used as a prayer for children to their parents. The Toba Batak language is one of the oldest proto-Malay tribes in Indonesia. The works in the Toba Batak language contain many meaningful works which are the wealth of Indonesian art. In this translation, the author will use translation techniques proposed by experts such as Newark and Catford. The original text of Ende Tanganku Na Metmet can be found in Tapanuli children's literature books as well as religious songbooks, especially the literary works of Toba Batak Christianity. The purpose of this study was to analyze the translation techniques of the song Tanganku Na Metmet which was translated into English.

METHOD(S)

The source language text is Toba Batak language and the target language text is Indonesian according to the translation rules. Then, from research on translation techniques, the contents and messages of literary works will be analyzed on the understanding and essence of translation objectives. Translation techniques are methods used to overcome translation difficulties at the word, sentence, or paragraph level. Hoed (1993) argues that translation techniques must follow applicable rules. Translation techniques according to Newmark (1988) consist of:

1. Transposition

Transposition is a translation technique that involves changing a grammatical form from the original language into a translation. Transpositions can be divided into two forms,

- a. This level shift occurs when the transposition produces elements of the original language that are different from elements of the translation language. Such shifts generally occur frequently from the grammatical level to the lexical level or vice versa.
- b. Category shifting occurs when transpositions result in native languages that differ in structure, word class, units, and systems. The category shift consists of structural shifts due to structural differences between the two languages involved in translation so that the equivalent structure of the original language differs from the structure of the translation language.

2. Modulation

Modulation is a structural shift that occurs in a transposition technique, which involves changes that involve a shift in meaning. It also changes the perspective, point of view, or other meaning terms or implied meanings. In a valid structural division, the modulation becomes:

- a. A shift in perspective occurs when the elements of the source language get their equivalent in a translated language that has a different semantic point of view.
- b. The shift in the scope of meaning occurs when the elements of the first language acquire a second equivalent/translation language which has a different scope of meaning, namely the broad scope of meaning to the narrow scope of meaning, or vice versa.

c. Descriptive translation provides a "description" that contains the meaning of the word in question because the translator cannot find a translation/equivalent of the word being translated. This can happen because the translator does not know or is not in the first language.

3. Culture Understanding

Cultural understanding which is also understood as contextual conditioning is carried out if the translator provides special words to explain words that are considered foreign by the reader of the translation. This is done so that the word is easy to understand. In addition, the translator's footnote as part of the supplementary explanation can also provide information in the form of a footnote to clarify the meaning of the translation word in question. The reason for this is because, without additional explanation, the word translation is not really well understood by the reader of the translation. In addition, phonological translation can also be done when the translator cannot find a suitable equivalent so that the translator can decide to make a new word that is taken from language adjustment. Adjustments can be done independently but adapted to the culture.

4. Word Omission

Omission means that the word is omitted / untranslated. This method can be taken if the meaning has been conveyed by certain elements or if a word/phrase is not so important. This is done because it is in the development of the text and will only distract the reader from the translation results and long explanations that are not so important.

In this study, the literary work of the song Tanganku Na Metmet was analyzed through descriptive qualitative research because the data came from local language literary works into the translated text. Bungin (2009) states that qualitative descriptive research aims to describe and summarize various conditions, situations, and phenomena of existing social reality. Then reality is drawn to the surface as characteristics, characters, properties, models, signs, or images of certain situations, conditions, or phenomena. In this study, the song Tanganku Na Metmet and its translation were analyzed using translation techniques. The data used in this study are primary data in the form of the native language, Toba Batak language, and translated text.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

The results in the analysis technique of the song Tanganku Na Metmet using the following techniques:

1) Transposition, intrasystem category shift (intra-category shift), 2) Modulation, which consists of a complete transfer of meaning. 3) Omission. 4) Understanding. According to Ambarstuti (2018), translation in the original language, especially regional languages into Indonesian, will be easier to translate and analyze properly when the translation of the translation is in the form of a verse or paragraph translation. To facilitate translation and analysis, the writer made the song Tanganku Na Metmet into four stanzas with standard translations and according to the original

text message. The original text of the song Tanganku Na Metmet is taken from Batak Toba literature which has been taught orally from generation to generation. However, in Batak Toba literacy, the song Tanganku Na Metmet has also been included in the Song of the Song of Christianity of Batak Toba Number 550 as a children's song.

Versi Bahasa Batak Toba Ende Tanganku Na Metmet

1. Tanganku na metmet, hulehon ma tu Debata.
Dainang i, na loja i, sai urupanku nama i,
Tanganki di Ho ma i. Tanganki di Ho ma i.
2. Nang pathu na metmet, hulehonma tu Debata,
Marlojong au suruon ni dainang i na loja i,
Nang pathi di Ho ma i. Nang pathi di Ho ma i.
3. Pangabas na metmet hulehon ma tu Debata,
Huapul ma dainang i, na jotjotan sai marsak i.
Hatangki di Ho ma i. Hatangki di Ho ma i.
4. Rohangku na metmet hulehon ma tu Debata.
Ingani i, o Tuhanki. Pasahat au tu surgomi.
Rohangki di Ho ma i. Rohangki di Ho ma i.

English Translation Version O My Little Hands

1. My little hand, offer it to my God.
Oh, my mother, tired you are, I will always help you,
I dedicate my hand to you, my hand I dedicate to you
2. Even my little feet, offer it to my God.
I'll be willing to run tired asked by my tired mother,
I dedicate my feet to you, my legs I dedicate to you.
3. My mouth is small, I offer it to my God.
I will comfort my mother, who is often sad.
Hold my words, hold my words.
4. My little heart I dedicate to my God.
Oh, my God, place it, so that I may be conveyed to Your Heaven,
My heart is only for you, my heart is only for you.

Discussion

Analysis

1. Transposition and Culture Understanding

Transposition is a translation technique that changes the changing form of grammar from the original language to the translation language. In this text, what is found is a category shift, a structural category shift is found in:

Native Text/Batak Toba

Marlojong au suruon ni dainang i na loja i...

Huapul ma dainang i, na jotjotan sai marsak i....

English Translation

I'm willing to run tired asked by my tired mother

I'll comfort my mother, who often grieves ...

Analysis: The four sentences if translated from words will eliminate the meaning and essence of literacy. "Marlojong", "Huapul" and "Ingani" are verbs meaning "tiring of running," "to cheer up" and "to occupy." Putting the verb / verbal at the beginning of the Batak Toba translation sentence in the context of the song will eliminate the element of singing. In Batak Toba literature, Toba's song is interpreted as a song that is sacred (to the Creator) or semi-sacred (to parents who are considered half God / God by the youth and children in the Tapanuli area).

2. Modulation

Modulation occurs due to structural shifts that occur in transposition techniques, which involve changes that involve shifting meaning. This also happens to change in perspective, perspective, or other aspects of understanding. In the song Tanganku Na Metmet, the author finds shifts in meaning found in:

Native Text/Batak Toba

...huapul ma dainang i, na jotjotan sai marsak i...

...hatangki di Ho ma i. Hatangki di Ho ma i....

English Translation

... I will comfort my mother, who is often sad ...

.... hold my words, hold my words

Analysis: The meaning of the translation "Huapul" and "Hatangki" when translated word for word has the meaning of "worship or praise" and "fruit of my words". This translation is not used in a direct translation because if the words are used they will not match the previous meaning and do not touch the essence of the literary work. The paraphrases in the translation are translated not according to the original translation but using words that are similar but adapted to their understanding so that they can have a literary essence.

3. Omission

The omission technique is done by deleting / not translating certain elements in the Toba Batak language into Indonesian because even without translating them, the message has been conveyed correctly. This method can be taken if the meaning has been conveyed by certain elements or if the word/phrase is not very important in the development of the text and will only disturb the English reader when translated in a long explanation. Omission techniques can be found at:

Native Text/Batak Toba

Rohangki di Ho ma i. Rohangki di Ho ma i.

English Translation

My heart is only for you, my heart is only for you.

Analysis: Literally translated, "Rohangki di Ho ma i" means "My soul only for you, my soul only for you". However, the use of these words will remove the essence of literature which is sacred praise and reverence. The use of "my heart is only for you" has the essence of praise and respect compared to "my soul for you alone" which has a mystical meaning that is considered in the Toba Batak culture and the Tapanuli community as mystical or heretical.

CONCLUSIONS

From this research, the writer concludes that the translation technique used in the translation of the text of the song Tanganku Na Metmet is translated into Indonesian, as follows:

1. Category Shift Transposition as well as cultural understanding which is a traditional transposition technique, and which consists of shifts in structure and intrasystem categories, occurs due to differences in the structure of each language. This is done by the author so that the translation results are easily written and understood by Indonesian readers. In addition, cultural similarity and understanding make it easier for readers to grasp the gist. The translation uses cultural equivalent techniques in this text so that the meaning and essence of the Toba Batak culture can be seen from the translation.
2. Modulation techniques, which consist of a shift in the point of view and a shift in the scope of meaning, are used by translators because of cultural differences in point of view and meaning. This is done by the translator so that the translation results are more comfortable to read in Indonesian without losing the meaning and essence of the purpose of the text. This in-text modulation translation technique makes the translated text easier to read and the reader can imagine the message very simply.
3. This mission is carried out by the author to provide additional information about the vocabulary so that the meaning is more easily understood by Indonesian readers. This is done because there are some vocabularies that do not exist in the national culture in general but are in the Toba Batak culture. So that to facilitate message delivery, the translator removes certain words or translates them into words that are more precise and integrated.

REFERENCES

- Ambarastuti. R.D (2018). *Analisis Teknik Penerjemahan Teks Cerita Rakyat Jepang Nezumi No Sumo Ke Dalam Bahasa Indonesia Tikus Dan Sumo* WWW.JITCO.OR.JP JLT – Jurnal Linguistik Terapan Volume 8, Nomor 1, Mei 2018 Politeknik Negeri Malang ISSN: 2088-2025
- Bungin. B. (2005). *Analisis Penelitian Data Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Catford, J.C. (1965). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Hoed. (2006). *Penerjemahan dan Kebudayaan*. Jakarta: Pustaka Jaya.
- Lembaga Alkitab Indonesia (2006). *Mateus – Suratannya Apostel*. Jakarta: LAI
- Nababan, M.R. (2008). *Teori Menerjemah Bahasa Inggris*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Newmark, Peter. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Hertfordshire: Prentice Hall International

English Language Teaching.

Nida E.A., Taber, C.R. (1982). *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Berlin: E.J. Brill.